

**FROM THE HISTORY OF THE STUDY OF ETHNIC GROUPS OF
BULUNGUR DISTRICT (EXAMPLE "QIRQ")**

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ABSTRACT. This article describes the history of the study of the Qirq tribe, one of the largest ethnic groups of the Uzbek people, the origin of the term Qirq, the author's views on the origin of the Qirq tribe and its geographical location.

Keywords: Tribe, region, people, nation, ethnogenesis, ethnic history, Kirkyuz, Ok-ko'yli, Kora-ko'yli, Karasirak, Karacha, Olmasa-un, Chaparashli, Balki, Jangaa (new), Chekli, Kochchekli, Chuvulloq, Boylar tupi, Kavush tupi, Oyuv (bear) to'pi, Beklar tupi.

It is claimed that studying the ethnogenesis and ethnic history of the Uzbek people is one of the complex issues of history. At the same time, this is one of the important problems of today. In the context of the independence of Uzbekistan and the ethno-cultural revival of the Uzbek people, in order to strengthen their understanding of national identity, it is of great importance to have deep historical knowledge and a clear understanding of the nation's rightful place in the ethnic diversity of the historical process.

Interest in the history of our country has been increasing since the years of independence. In particular, the desire to study issues such as the ethnic composition of our people, the origin of the Uzbek people, ethnogenesis, the history, composition, structure of clans and tribes, and the geographical location of Uzbek clans is increasing among our people.

There is not any nation in the world that is made up of a single clan or tribe, Uzbek people as well. It is noted in historical sources that Uzbeks consist of 92 major clans. In particular, Turdi Faroghi, a major representative of Uzbek classic literature in the 17th century, calls these clans together and says:

Tor ko'ngullik beklar, manman demang,

kenglik qiling,

To'qson ikki bo'li (qarindosh) o'zbek yurtidur,

tenglik qiling.

Birni qipchoqu xitoyu birni yuz,

nayman demang,

Qirqu yuz, ming son bo'lub, bir xon

oyinlik qiling

It is obvious from the poem that the great poet calls the 92 Uzbek clans to live in solidarity.

The Qirqs (40) are one of the 92 clans of the Uzbek people. Scattered around Samarkand, Panjikent, present. They lived in Gallaorol, Jizzakh, Zomin and Oratepa regions. One of the tribes that were part of the Uzbek people - they lived mixed with the Uzbeks. Therefore, it is also known as "Kirkyuz" in many sources. Qirq (forty), Yuz (hundred) and Ming (thousand) tribes were called by the common name of Marqa. Ethnogenesis of the Forties is related to the Dashti Kipchak Uzbeks. Forties have been divided into several clans in the past. The largest of them are: Ok-koyli (white-sheep), Kora-koyli (black-sheep), Karasirak, Karacha, Olmasa-un, Chaparashli and others. Until the beginning of the 20th century, they lived in a semi-sedentary manner, engaged in animal husbandry, part of them lived on the slopes of the mountains, in the hills, engaged in rainfed and irrigated agriculture.

As it is said, according to tradition, the Turko-Mongol cavalryman who went into a battle carried his family and clans together. When Shaibani Khan brought an army to Movarounnahr, 92 cavalymen served in his army.

J. Begimkulov in his article "From the history of the study of Uzbek clans (in the example of faces)" provides the following information: according to the story about the origin of the term "Yuz", China (Turkish) king sent first forty, then one hundred horsemen towards the West, and they settled here and their descendants were called the Qirq (Forties) and the Yuz (Hundreds). Today, there are similar stories among the Qirq and Yuz clans living in Bulung'ur district in Samarkand.

The Qirq (Forties) is the third largest number after the Ming (thousand) and the Yuz (hundred) among the clans and tribes of the 92-member Uzbek people. Elderly call him the brother of the face. In fact, it is probably correct to call the thousand, hundred and forty ethnic associations that have arisen as a result of political associations (associations). For now we will call them "tribe".

Qirq tribes live mainly in Gallaorol and Bulung'ur districts of Samarkand region and Jizzakh and Zomin districts of Syrdarya region, partly also in Bekobad and Oratepa regions. Qirq tribes is first divided into 6 large pieces (families). These are: Karakoyli, Karacha, Moltop, Mulkush, Chaprashli and Chortkesar. According to grandfather Kholbota, who lives in the village of Uzunbulok of Gallaorol district, a piece of forty is divided into 4: balki, jang'gaa (new), kheti, kochchekli, chuvulloq.

According to grandfather Sayfin, who lives in Moltop village of Gallaorol district, the Moltop section of Kirq is divided into 4: Boylar tupi, Kavush tupi, Oyuv (bear) tupi and Beklar tupi. In addition to these, among the Qirq living in Gallaorol, Jizzakh, Bulung'ur regions, there are Quya bosh, Ko'k gumboz qirq, Sug'unboy, Quyonquloqli, Qoshiq buloq, To'kcho'ra, Uch qiz, Qo'sh qavut qirq, Qora chivar, uyuvli are also found.

Nowadays representatives of the Qirq clans live in Bulung'ur, Jomboy, Aqdarya, Payariq, Tailoq and Ko'shrabot districts of Samarkand region. The distribution of Qirq clans in Bulung'ur district is as follows:

1. Qirq (Ingichka village)
2. Qirq (Kuyonqirq)
3. Qirq (Katqirq village)
4. Qirq (Jomonjor village)
5. Qirq (Kaptarkhana village)
6. Qirq (Kirqshodi village)
7. Qirq (Botabad district)
8. Qirq (Mingtepa village)
9. Qirq (Mongolian village)
10. Qirq (Kattaqishlaq village)
11. Qirq (Qiyon village)
12. Qirq (Aqariq village)

In conclusion, we can say that the Uzbeks, one of the ancient peoples, are composed of many ethnic groups. There are twelve ethnic groups of our people in Bulung'ur district. In historical sources, it is noted that Uzbeks consist of 92 large clans, and these clans, in turn, are divided into large shahobchas, shahobchas into small pieces, pieces into balls, balls into fathers and divided into dynasties. At the end of the article, it should be emphasized that in addition to identifying the ethnic groups of our people, studying its ethnic history and enlightening our youth with the contribution of our ancestors to the world civilization is an urgent task of today.

References:

1. Shoniyozov K. The formation process of the Uzbek people. — Tashkent: 2001, p.3
2. Elmurodov N. Ethnic groups of the Uzbek people of the Zarafshan oasis – Samarkand, 2008, p.4
3. UzME. Volume 1. Tashkent, 2000, p.155
4. Askarov A. Ethnogenesis and ethnic origin of the Uzbek people. Tashkent, 2007, p.229

5. J.Begimqulov, Xushboqov J. A collection of scientific articles on the history of the study of Uzbek clans – Tashkent, 2016, p. 25
6. Doniyorov X, Genealogies and dialects of the Uzbek people. - Tashkent, 1968, p.86